

ADOPTION: THE CREATOR OF RELATIONS

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Abstract:

Former Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru rightly said that, “The children of today will make the India of tomorrow. The way we bring them up will determine the future of the country”. Likewise children are considered to play an important role in the society as well as in family. But there are many families, who are longing to have a child but could not have one for various reasons like infertility or not able to carry a child on their own term or if the parent is a single parent and is ready to start a family or if the parents are of same sex couples and want to raise a child together. In the following cases “Adoption” acts as torchlight in removing the darkness of not having a child. Even many foster children gets a new family and learn about relationship, love, bonding etc., In India, there are many laws governing adoption such as the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956; the Guardian and Wards Act, 1890; adoption under Muslim Law, Christian and Parsi Law; the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act, 2000 etc., In this article, the authors would like to throw light on the concept adoption, its benefits, the reason for adoption, laws governing adoption in India, adoption in other countries and international adoption.

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Introduction:

Giving birth to a child is a precious moment and a gift to the couple. But, what if the female is unable to reproduce or the couple faces any other problems. Here, adoption plays a vital role in their life. Through adoption new relationship emerges between the couple and the child. New life begins for them. The child will get parents and a family and the same is in the side of the parents too. Through adoption, it accomplishes the lifelong desire of raising the child and building new meaningful relationships. Adoption is a legal process and makes a connection socially and emotionally to both the parents and the child. In this article, the authors strive to discuss the theme of adoption, procedure and many other related concepts.

Meaning:

The authors would encourage the readers to know the meaning of the term “adoption”, its classification and meaning of other words related to adoption.

Adoption:

The word “Adoption”, hit from the Old French word “Adoptare”, which means “To choose for oneself”. Adoption is considered to be a Legal Proceedings, which creates a bond of a Parent-Child relation between the persons who are not related by blood. In other words, it means, the act of taking another person’s child legally into one’s family in order to raise that child as their own natural child. The legal adoption naturally transfers all the rights and responsibilities permanently to the adopted parents from the biological parents. The person who is adopting the child would be named as “Prospective Adoptive Parents” (PAP), Foster, or Adoptive parents.

Classification of Adoption:

Adoption is a way of getting a child or a baby from the adoption agency for those who cannot become parents biologically. So, for those couples who really loves to have children goes with adoption. From the adoption agency, those couples through legal process will take the child who will be his/her parents and they will be responsible for raising the child and for its well-being. For those couples who would opt for adoption, they have to get some knowledge in the types. Various types of adoption prevail in India. Those adoptions depend upon the adoptive parents and the birth mother.

The following are the types of adoption followed in India;

- 1) Open Adoption
- 2) Semi- Open Adoption
- 3) Closed Adoption
- 4) Intra- Family Adoption (aka) Relative Adoption
- 5) Domestic Adoption
- 6) International Adoption

The authors would like to explain these types of adoption in brief.

1) Open Adoption:

Open adoption is an adoption where the Birth Mother and the Adoptive Parents have contacts with each other. The open adoption involves a contact between the parties. The birth mother will often keep in touch with the adoptive parents through phone calls, messages, letters etc. This is granted when the child reaches the age of 18 years in other words when the child becomes major.

2) Semi- Open Adoption:

Semi- Open Adoption is also known as Mediation Adoption. This type of adoption means there is an indirect contact between Birth Parents and the Adoptive Parents. In other words, both the parties do not have a direct contact. However, the adoptive parents will send letters to the birth mother or they will contact the birth mother through the adoptive agency. This kind of contact will be in progress until the adopted child attains the majority age which is considered as legal in law. This Semi- Open Adoption shall be converted to either Open Adoption or the Closed Adoption at any point of time.

3) Closed Adoption:

Exactly, there is no contact between the adoptive parents and the birth mother. This kind of adoption is called as Closed Adoption. Any type of information or contact will not be passing on to both set of parties. Sometimes, the medical information about the birth mother will be known by the adoptive parent but, mostly, it is prohibited and that is illegal as there is a strict enforcement. The law has been made stricter in cases when a child is recaptured from an abusive society.

4) Intra Family Adoption (aka) Relative Adoption:

As the name suggests, Intra Family Adoption means adopting a child within the family. Intra family adoption is also known as Relative Adoption. This adoption takes place when the biological parents of the child passed away or any one of the parents either mother or father remarries or they are not in a position to take care and raise the child, the relative will adopt the child or the step parents will adopt the child and that adoption will be taken place legally. The child stays within the biological family but the important decisions to be taken of the child will be made by the adoptive parents.

5) Domestic Adoption:

Domestic means someone's family, Home Country, or Home. Domestic Adoption generally means adoption within the country. The adoption can occur from any state but it should be taken place within the country. The couple who wishes to adopt have to register in any recognized government agency. After registering with the government agencies, the investigating officer will inquire and verify the particulars about the adoptive parents and check whether they are eligible to raise a child. If the investigating officer is satisfied and the formalities are fulfilled, the couple is ready to adopt the child. The domestic adoption is less expensive.

6) International Adoption:

When the couple wishes to adopt a child from the birth parents and the adoptive parents or the birth mother is not from the same country (.i.e.) either of the party is from other country then, that type of adoption is called as International Adoption. So, this adoption involves adopting a child from a foreigner. In other words, bequeathing the child to the adoptive parents who are not a native citizen. In most of the countries, the international adoption laws vary. In some countries, they don't even follow International Adoption. Domestic adoption is dominant in India. In adoption hierarchy, the first preference is Domestic adoption; secondly, the preference is given to the Non- Resident India (NRIs), and lastly to the International Citizens is given the preference for international adoption in India. Orphaned children will be adopted mostly in International adoption so that the birth parents may not be involved.

A couple who is interested in adopting a child may choose any type of adoption specified in the aforesaid categories.

Eligibility for the Adoptee to adopt:

As mentioned earlier, the couple who is ready to adopt a child will be called as “Prospective Adoptive Parents” (PAP). The PAP should not be an insane, must have a good health so that their health issues does not affect the child after adoption. And also, they should be capable enough to provide a good future to the child providing education, and good circumstances. Irrespective of the Marital Status, anybody can adopt. Any male Hindu who is of a sound mind and is not a minor has the capacity to take a son or a daughter in adoption¹. Under Old Law, adoption of a daughter or a girl is impermissible but now it is not so. Any female Hindu who is of a sound mind and is not a minor has the capacity to take a son or daughter in adoption². Even though, the couple has a biological child, they can adopt but, if they have 3 children, they cannot opt for adoption. If a married couple likes to adopt a child, they can adopt only after 2 years of their marriage life. So that their marital status will be strong after the 2 year time period³. And also, the consent of the wife is considered to be necessary if the male is adopting⁴.

Procedure to Adopt:

A Family is considered as an essential part in one's life. Where there are elders, children, grandparents, parents, son and daughters it is considered as a typical family. What if a couple cannot have child on their own? Adoption plays a major role in this part. Through adoption, a couple can get a child and raise that child as their own baby and they will become parents and for a child who was abandoned by their birth mother and father, he/she will get a family. Adoption is made to create a family where they share their love, care and every sort of positivity. To adopt, there are many steps involved. Let us, see what are all the steps involved in Adoption.

- ✓ Decide whether adoption is right for you
- ✓ Have a talk with the adoption professionals
- ✓ Find a perfect adopting parents to create a best future for the baby
- ✓ Contact the adoptive parents and know their importance for adoption before adoption process starts
- ✓ Finalize the adoption and start a new family.

Let us see in detail about the aforesaid steps.

¹The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, S 7.

²The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, S 8.

³Adoption Regulations, 2017 and Juvenile Justice Act, 2015.

⁴ *Id.* at 1.

✓ **Decide whether adoption is right for you:**

If a couple does not have child for years, but they are yearning to have a baby, the best choice is adoption. But, in our society mostly the elders does not have much interest in adoption. So, the couple will not have any idea about it. First, the couple who is willing to have a child has to discuss for many times and if they are comfortable and strong enough they can go for adoption. Both the spouses should have in their mind that, the child which is going to be adopted is their own child and they should treat him/her as their own child. If they are not satisfied with adoption, then it is not right for them to adopt a baby.

✓ **Have a talk with the Adoption Professionals:**

After deciding to adopt a child, the couple have to approach the nearby adoption professionals, so that they will inform all the legal works and how to adopt and they will have a counselling session for them for adoption. Then, if the couple is willing to adopt, they have to register and after the legal works are completed, they are ready for adopting a child.

✓ **Find a Perfect Adopting Parents to create a best future for the baby:**

It is in the part of the birth parents who would like to give the baby for adoption. The birth parents would have many reasons for giving the baby for adoption. If they are not economically stable to raise the child, they can give the baby for adoption. So, they have to find a perfect and good family for the process of adoption. They should be satisfied whether the adoptee is capable enough to create a good environment for the child to grow and they are eligible to provide education and a best future.

✓ **Contact the adoptive parents and know their importance for adoption before adoption process starts:**

After the birth parents are satisfied with the adoptive parent's capabilities, they have to contact the adopting parents through the adoption professionals to know why they have approached for adopting a child and they will get more information relating to adopting a child. If the birth parents got the answer for all their confusions, queries and they are satisfied with the adoptive parent's life and reason for adoption they will start the process for adoption.

✓ **Finalize the Adoption and start a new Family:**

If all the legal proceedings end well, the investigation about the adoptive parents are done and both the parties are satisfied and ready for adoption, they can adopt the child and the adopting couple will become the parents for that child and all the important decision about the child have to be taken only by them. They are sole responsible for the conduct of the child. They should treat the child as their own child and they will become a family.

Child:

Child means, “Every Human Being below the age of 18 years Unless, under the law applicable to the child, Majority is attained earlier”⁵. Therefore, whoever, below the age of 18 years are considered as a child under the International Law.

The Child means, “Whoever has not attained the age of 14 years”⁶

Likewise, the definition of the term child has been made differently in many different laws. So, the exact meaning and the age group for the word child has not been defined in Indian law. So, there arises many confusions and it is vague.

For Adoption purpose, the child must be an Orphan, Abandoned or Surrendered Child who is legally free for adoption and that is declared by the child welfare committee. For adoption, even the child below the age of 4 can be adopted. There is no specified age limit for the purpose of adoption. Even a New born baby is eligible to be adopted.

Child Abandoned:

A Child who is intentionally and willingly left by his/her natural parents is known as abandoned child. There are two kinds of child abandonment. That is, Open Abandonment and Secret Abandonment.

- ✓ The Open Abandonment means, “A child is left intentionally by leaving all the identities of the birth parents is known as Open Abandonment and whose intention is not to return back to the child and to leave all the parental responsibilities”.
- ✓ Secret Abandonment means, “A child is left behind here also by his/her birth parents and they were willingly does so and did not left their identity” is known as Secret

⁵The Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989. art 1.

⁶ The Child Labour (Protection and Regulation) Act, 1986, S 2(ii).

abandonment and they also left the child to relinquish from the parental responsibilities and their intention is not to return back to the child.

Child Protection:

Child Protection means providing a shield to the children against the assault, exploitation, abuse etc., For the purpose of protecting and safeguarding the child, the government made a system called as “Child Protection System” to protect the children who are minors against any harmful activity and to encourage the stability of the family.

Child Protection System means “A set of Laws, Rules and Regulations, Policies which is a need across all the social sectors mainly in social welfare, education, health, security to support prevention and to respond to the protection- related risks”.⁷

Reason for child being adopted:

Everyone has different life and different stories. Every person who comes to adopt a child has different backgrounds and various reasons for adoption. Few commonly identified reasons for adoption are because the adoptive parents struggled a lot with infertility or being Homosexuals who want to have a child or wanting for a male child and many more reasons prevails.

➤ **Struggling Due to Infertility:**

The couple who yearns for starting a family may face conflicts relating to infertility. For them, to start a family, adoption gives a new beginning to start a life. It gives them a hope and an opportunity to raise a child. Adoption builds meaningful relationship to live their life.

➤ **Being Homosexuals:**

Adoption allows these couples to share a life with the adopted child and relish a unique experience of parenthood. And also, the couples will be strong enough to live in this world as a family.

➤ **Adoption by Widow:**

⁷According to United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund (UNICEF).

A widow or divorcee or a spinster irrespective of her marital status can adopt a child for herself. The Supreme Court held that on adoption by a widow, the adopted son is to be deemed to be a member of the family of the deceased husband of the widow⁸.

➤ **Wanting for a Male Child:**

Some couples may not have male child. So, due to family pressure or any other reason, the couples eagerly want for a baby boy. If they couldn't have a boy child naturally, they will go for adoption. In some other cases, certain couples will leave the female child in orphanage and in return they will adopt a boy child. But this scenario is not prevailing now-a-days. In earlier years, this would have been the situation before every one becomes educated.

➤ **Rape:**

Due to Physical Abuse or forceful sex with the female who are unmarried, leads to pregnancy. For them, who doesn't know what to do next gives birth to a child. and leaves the child in orphanage. The adoptive parents who want to start a family, will seek the adoptive center and give life and family to those children.

➤ **Teenage Pregnancy:**

From the heading itself, it is understood that, teenage pregnancy of the girls will also lead the child homeless. Those children will be taken care by some institution, adoption centers etc.

Rights involved in Adoption:

In adoption, both the adoptive parents and adoptive child has certain rights. We will see what are the rights vested in both the parties in accordance with adoption.

➤ **Rights of the Adoptive Child:**

Every natural child will have certain rights from their parents. It may either be in property, profits & losses, responsibilities etc., same rights will be vested to the adoptive children. There is no discrimination in rights between the natural child and the adopted child. Like the class 1 heirs the adopted child is also eligible for bequeathing the property of their parents. So, from this it is understandable that, the adopted child is designated to inherit from the adoptive father like the biological child. According to Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956 envisages that, the

⁸Sawan Ram & Others v. Kala Wanti & Others, (1967) 3 SCR 687.

adopted children will not have any right from their biological father. The child cannot marry any person whom he or she not have married if he or she could not have married if he or she had continued in the birth family⁹. And also, any Property which vested in the adopted child before the adoption shall continue to vest in such person¹⁰. At last, the child cannot divest any person of any property of any estate which vested in him or her before the adoption¹¹.

➤ **Rights of the Adoptive Parents:**

The Adoptive parents must acquire the knowledge regarding the health information about the child. And they must attend the counselling service in 3 phases(i.e.) pre, during and post adoption. They should know all the legal paper work before entering into adoption. They should be emotionally stable because if they are not emotionally stable, then how can they raise the adoptive child in the society. They should have broad and open mind regarding adoption and they should not ill-treat the adopted child.

Adoption in India:

In India, the practice of adoption has been followed since ancient period. Back then adoption was considered to be a sacramental act. But in this modern era adoption is opted due to various reasons as stated above. The concept of adoption is governed by various laws in India and they are as follows;

Laws relating to adoption in India:

i. **The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956:**

This act is applicable to a Hindu, Buddhist, Jain or Sikh. Christians, Muslims, Jews and Parsis are excluded from the definition of this act. Any Hindu male who is of a sound mind, eligible and not a minor can adopt a son or daughter with the consent of his partner if she is alive or competent to give her consent. Similarly, any Hindu female who is not married or her husband is not alive or obtained divorce or her husband has been declared has incompetent by the Court has the capacity to adopt a child. As stated before, only Hindus can adopt under this act subject to certain criteria. They are,

⁹ The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, S 12(a).

¹⁰ The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, S 12(b).

¹¹ The Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956, S 12(c).

- ✓ At the time of adoption there should not be any living son in the succeeding three generations either by legitimate blood relation or through adoption, if the adoption is of a son by any Hindu male or female.
- ✓ Accordingly, one should not have a daughter or son's daughter at the time of adoption in cases of adoption of a daughter by any Hindu male or female.
- ✓ The adoptive father should be at least twenty one years older to the child if he is adopting a daughter.
- ✓ The adoptive mother should be at least twenty one years older to the child if she is adopting a son.

ii. The Guardian and Wards Act, 1890:

There is no separate adoption law for Muslims, Christian or Parsis in India. If they want to legally adopt a child, they are required to approach the Court under the Guardians and Wards Act, 1890. Under this Act, there exists only a guardian and ward relationship between the adopted child and parents. In contrary to Hindu Adoption act, in the Guardian and Wards Act the adopted child can break his relationship from the family once he attained majority [i.e.] 21 years. Further, legal right of inheritance will not be available to such adopted child.

If a foreigner wants to adopt an Indian child, such adoption can be made under this act. It is an essential requirement that the foreigner adoptee has to give an assurance to the court that within 2 years of arrival of the adopted child in their country, the adoption of the child would be legally made as per the laws of their country.

iii. Adoption under Muslim Law:

In the case of Mohammed Allahabad Khan v. Mohammed Ismail¹², it was held that Mohammedan Law has nothing in similar in adoption as recognized in Hindu system. However, the right of adoption for Muslims was extended by a landmark judgment given by the Supreme Court in the case of Shabnam Hashmi v. Union of India, where it was stated that the right to adopt a child would prevail over every personal laws and religious codes in the country as per the provisions of Juvenile Justice Act¹³. Under Muslim Law acknowledgement of paternity is the

¹² (1886) 8 ILR 234.

¹³ (2014) 4 SCC 1.

nearest approach to adoption. The paternity of the child is established upon the Muslim person when he acknowledges the child to be his legitimate child.

iv. Adoption under Christian and Parsi Law:

Here adoption is done by obtaining permission from the Court under section 8 of the Guardian and Wards Act, 1890. As similar to Muslim Law here also the child is considered as ward and not an adoptive child and once the child turned 21 then he is considered to be an individual identity.

v. The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act, 2000:

The term legal adoption has been defined under section 2(aa)¹⁴, which states that adoption means, “when an adoptive child becomes the legitimate child of the adoptive parents with all the rights and privileges vested in that relationship and is permanently separated from his biological parents”. Section 57 of Juvenile Justice Act, 2015 states about the capacity of a male and female to adopt.

- ✓ A girl child cannot be adopted by a single male.
- ✓ At least two years of stable marital relationship is required for a couple to adopt a child.
- ✓ A minimum age of at least twenty one should be between the adopted child and parents.

Persons who are eligible for adopting in India:

There are not that many restrictions on person's eligibility to adopt in India. The following persons are allowed to adopt a child;

- ✓ An Indian whether he is married or not;
- ✓ A foreigner (i.e.) a person of any nationality;
- ✓ Or a Non- Resident Indian.
- ✓ The prospective parents are required to be mentally sound and physically fit.
- ✓ The adoptive parents should be absolutely prepared to adopt a child and should be ready to afford good upbringing.

Adoption in other countries:

¹⁴ Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Amendment Act, 2006.

i. USA

There is a very positive view for adoption by the Americans. Awareness for adoption is raised on November 23 each year in US which is considered as the National Adoption Day. A favorable view is shown by half of the Americans towards adoption through foster care system. In a survey conducted by the YouGov, it was found that around half of the Americans, knows a friend or a family member who is adopted. And, also a friend or a family member who is an adoptive parent.¹⁵In a manner of encouragement, adoption subsidies and financial support are given to foster parents in America to spend towards their child needs.

ii. UK

Similar to adoption in States, in UK, financial support, adoption allowance etc., are provided to the adoptive parents. The adoptive parents are guaranteed similar rights of obtaining adoption pay and leave entitlements as that of birth parents. 52 weeks of adoption leave is granted to adoptive parents. And an adoption pay of 39 weeks is also granted. Apart from the statutory adoption leave, there are many other post adoption benefits granted to the adoptive parents in UK. Such as,

- Child benefits and tax credits.
- Carer's Allowance.
- Adoption Support Fund and Adoption support from local authority.
- Disability living allowance for children.
- 'Settling in grant' for adopters.
- Child and Adolescent Mental Health Services¹⁶.

International Adoption:

An individual or a couple becoming legal and permanent parents of a child who is a national of a different country is known as International adoption or transnational adoption. In such

¹⁵ Jamie Ballard, *Americans have Positive Views of Adoption*, YouGov (Nov. 21, 2019, 7:00 PM), <https://today.yougov.com/topics/lifestyle/articles-reports/2019/11/20/adoption-poll-survey-family-foster-care>

¹⁶ *After Adoption: What Help Can We Get?*, Havering London Borough (Mar. 25, 2022, 5:00 PM), <https://familyserviceshub.havering.gov.uk/kb5/havering/directory/advice.page?id=WdZ0bmxp7KQ#:~:text=Adoption%20pay%20and%20leave,-Adoption%20pay%20is%20equal%20to.share%20parental%20leave%20and%20pay.>

transnational adoption, prospective adoptive parents are required to fulfill the legal adoption requirements of their country and the requirements of the country whose nationality the child holds.

Intercountry adoption is followed in India also. India is a party in respect to international adoption with the Hague Convention on Protection of Children and Co- operation. All the Indian laws are applicable to prospective adoptive parents in case of international adoption. For instance, under Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act of 1956, the Guardians and Wards Act of 1890, or the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act of 2000 a child can be legally placed with prospective parents.

Difficulties faced by adoptive child in India:

With the never ending paper works, long wait lists and legal wrangles adoption in India is not as easy as it looks. It is shown in a data that only 2317 children are available for adoption whereas there are 29000 prospective parents are willing to adopt¹⁷. This may lead to increase in the length of adoption process. This disparity occurs due to abandoning the children and the children are vulnerable to physical violence, sexual abuse, trafficking and poor care.

Amidst 2017 to 2019, there was an unusual act of returning adoptive children by the prospective parents after adopting. A data from Central Adoption Resource Authority shows that 60 percent of children returned were girls and 24 percent were children with special needs and 6 percent are children who are of elder more than age six¹⁸. This is due to children with special needs and older age has difficulties in adapting to the new environment and new family.

Challenges faced in adoption:

Adopting a child has the following challenges and problems such as;

i. Financial challenge:

Depending upon the adoption agency, the financial aspect of adoption varies. Compared to public agencies one may have to pay high terms of adoption fee in private adoption agency.

¹⁷ *The Challenges and Undressed Issues of Child Adoption Practices in India*, The Wire (May. 10, 2021, 8.00 AM), <https://thewire.in/society/challenges-issues-child-adoption-practices-india>

¹⁸ *Id.* at 17.

ii. **Health issues:**

Both in open and closed adoption it is impossible to know the complete history of child's health. This causes lots of problems in taking proper care of the child and assessing the financial aspect of child's healthcare.

There are also many other challenges like emotional challenge, ethical, cultural challenges, legal challenge etc.,

Conclusion:

Therefore, adoption is a beautiful act of building relationship within the family, sharing and showing love and bonding with each other. It helps many foster kids to experience the love of living in a family. Adoption also helps the foster parents to build a family. The Indian law gives importance to the concept adoption as well ensures the safety of the foster children by imposing various rules. The only drawback is, there should be more stringent laws in preventing unregistered foster care centers which misuses children. Also, the procedure for adoption should be made easier with fewer steps because most of the people fear to adopt due to the long process involved in the adoption procedure.

“The World may not change if one adopts a child but for that child the world changes”.

